

QUIZ

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PROGRAM CODE : DMCR
COURSE CODE : ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6 (SIX)
INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MS Word 2013 on Windows 10 Home

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Cleenewerck and Gulma (2019) frowned at plagiarism as a practice that should not be tolerated in this course. It is therefore relevant to mention the source of your information on the following grounds:**
 - Though unethical, plagiarism adds value to your research and provides a basis for the readership to follow and extend your research.*
 - Plagiarism is wrong and unethical, as it is unfair to take someone's work without giving credit, thus resulting into an academic crime that could have serious consequences.***¹
 - Failing to acknowledge someone's work at EUCLID means losing a few marks, however, most brilliant defaulting students have been able to make good grades, thus underscoring the fact that plagiarism is not as serious as illegalized by EUCLID.*
 - Plagiarism is unethical and must not be practiced at EUCLID and just a few U.K based universities.*

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2019), 2. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed June 12, 2020).

2. **Although EUCLID recommends using American English, but the Standard British English (SBE) is also acceptable. Which of the following set of spellings fully corresponds with the Standard British English (SBE) style?**
- Center, Color, Plough*
 - Organization, Ax, Colour*
 - Plough, Axe, Centre.***²
 - Honour, Colour, Plow*
3. **In his book devoted to academic writing, Soles (2009) states that good academic writing is first and foremost defined by so called ‘ISCE’ which stands for :**
- Intelligence, Substance, Clarity, and Energy.***³
 - Intelligence, Substance, Comprehensive and Energy*
 - Intelligence, Synergy, Clarity and Energy*
 - Intelligence, Synergy, Clarity and Efficiency*
4. **Developing and presenting a literature review remains one of the daunting tasks involved in writing a dissertation, as it entails reviewing topic-specific literature. In a nutshell, the purpose and function of literature review,**
- Involves categorizing participant responses*

² Ibid, 28.

³ Derek Soles, *The Essentials of Academic Writing* (Boston, MA: Cengage Learning, 2009), 6.

- Entails the stage at which the research problem is to be addressed in the context of history, background and other issues germane to the problem.*
 - Involves the systematic identification, location and analysis of material related to the research problem.* ⁴
 - Gives a full assessment of the research problems and provides a synergy between data presentation and data analysis
5. **Most researchers have been confusing a topic with a research problem. While a topic refers to a general area of interest, a research problem,**
- Is more specific and it seeks to understand some aspects of the general topic.* ⁵
 - Clears understanding of the purposes and functions behind each of the parts of the research paper.*
 - Interrogates a superficial idea of what each part of the dissertation is intended for.*
 - Differentiates between well-researched and poorly-researched problems.*
6. **Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* documents what citation style?**
- MLA*
 - APA*

⁴ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 46.

⁵ Ibid.

*Chicago.*⁶

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7. In her book, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, Kate Turabian outlines two citation skills, which are:

*Note-bibliography style and author-date style.*⁷

Book-date style and title-bibliography style.

Title-date style and title-bibliography style.

Author-note style and book-date style.

8. Secondary data can include which of the following:

Specialized encyclopedias.

Dictionaries.

Scholarly journals

*All of the Above.*⁸

⁶ Kale L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 11.

⁷ Ibid, 85-87.

⁸ Ibid, 24-25.

9. Which of the following can be the source of primary data in research?

- Data collected through observations and experiments.*⁹
- Censuses Data and newspapers.*
- Survey and censuses*
- Survey and reference.*

10. Adopting ethical considerations in research means:

- Deception is only used when necessary.*
- Selected informants give the comment.*
- Minimizing potential harm to those involved in the study.*¹⁰
- The research is anonymous.*

⁹ Ibid, 24-25

¹⁰ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 76.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. **Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.**

EUCLID. 2019. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. **Washington DC: Euclid University, 2019.** <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2020).

Soles, Derek. *The Essentials of Academic Writing*. **Boston, MA: Cengage Learning, 2009.**

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. **Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.**

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.